

Project No. 964220

Intelligent digital tools for screening of brain connectivity and dementia risk estimation in people affected by mild cognitive impairment

Deliverable 7.1

Website establishment and focus group organisation

WP 7 – Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
H2020	Horizon 2020
WP	Work Package

Partner Short Names

OUS	Oslo University Hospital
AALTO	Aalto University
accelCH	accelopment Schweiz AG
AE	Alzheimer Europe
Brainsymph	BrainSymph AS
DNV	Det Norske Veritas-Germanischer Lloyd® Group
HUS	Helsinki University Hospital
IRCCS	Scientific Institute for Research, Hospitalization and Healthcare, San Raffaele Roma
Lurtis	Lurtis Rules S.L
Neuroconnect	Neuroconnect Srl
OsloMET	Oslo Metropolitan University
Radboundmc	Radboud University Medical Center
TLU	Tallinn University
UCM	Complutense University of Madrid
UCSC	Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable is part of the Work Package (WP) 7, task 7.4: “Communication”. It refers to the subtask of establishing the AI-Mind project website, which will be maintained and updated regularly throughout the project’s five years and after its completion.

The website serves as the main source of information about AI-Mind, with up-to-date content relevant to the project, (which is) designed for different target audiences.

This deliverable reports the main objectives and strategy for maintaining the website, as well as provides detailed information on the structure, technical implementation, and outlook, considering the different target groups.

With over 460,000,000 internet users in the European Union alone¹, a website can be a powerful instrument to communicate and spread information. The project website hence serves as a flexible tool that allows the AI-Mind consortium to raise awareness of the project and to provide up-to-date, consistent, and complete information to its various stakeholders. To ensure that the website aligns with the AI-Mind objectives, it will include a dedicated section in different languages which will facilitate the recruitment of participants to the study.

2 Key facts

- Website address: <https://www.ai-mind.eu/>
- The website has been continuously expanded and updated over the first three months of the project. At the time of submitting this deliverable website is under work incorporating advanced features for recruitment purposes.
- accelCH has created the website using WordPress and is responsible for its maintenance.
- The project website is securely hosted on accelCH’s webserver.

3 Aims & objectives

The main aim of the website is to raise awareness of the project and keep the various stakeholders interested throughout the project duration. In addition, the website aims to present not only the scope of the project but also the consortium, establishing a network of experts in both the health and scientific sectors.

Website maintenance includes updates of the event calendar which aims to increase interest with relevant webinars, conferences, and workshops. Moreover, with a dedicated area for the AI-Mind study, we aim to encourage participants and general physicians to contact the AI-Mind team.

The “Study participants” and “For professionals” pages will include study-relevant content. These pages complement the main objectives of the website. Therefore, the main aim of the above-mentioned pages is not only to provide comprehensive information about the AI-Mind study but also

¹ <https://www.internetworldstats.com/europa.htm>

to be an engaging and useful platform for direct contact with the AI-Mind research team performing the study and follow-up actions.

4 Strategy

The website is the focal point for all stakeholders to access project-relevant information. The easy-to-grasp navigation pane allows visitors to select the page of their interest. The website was set up with pages tailored to different focus groups, identified during the stakeholder analysis, carried out for the AI-Mind project. Within this task, we organized stakeholders in six clusters: i) healthcare providers, ii) patient's advocacy interested in dementia prevention, iii) the scientific community of the university and clinical researchers, iv) policymakers on national and European level, v) private sector with a focus on health and data management, and vi) the general public.

Further grouping within given clusters allowed to specify focus groups based on their relation towards the project. For example, researchers in neuroscience have a greater interest in AI-Mind than mathematicians. Whereas the landing page provides up-to-date information about the AI-Mind-related activities and news, other pages are subject-specific and address different target groups. For instance, dedicated pages to support recruitment for the AI-Mind study, with defined areas for both participants and professionals are under development. It is designed to be a user-friendly platform with the possibility to express interest in participation. Content will be tailored for target groups by use of everyday language for participants and technical language for professionals.

The "News & Events" page is updated on a regular basis with information about the research activities, results, opportunities (for the research community), and relevant events are marked on the calendar. All project outcomes will be promptly communicated and accompanied with visual representation. Moreover, the AI-Mind Twitter account complements the news section on the landing page by feeding with content as soon as "tweet" is published.

Next to Twitter, other social media platforms, such as Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, and YouTube are linked to the website for easy access and the possibility to follow project activity there. Depending on the platform, different strategies are implemented and thus triggering the interest of various stakeholders to visit the AI-Mind website.

Due to the increased popularity of short videos published online, audio-visual materials, like interviews with project partners or explanatory videos, will be integrated into the website and published on the AI-Mind YouTube channel throughout the project.

Moreover, tailor-made material such as factsheets, infographics, flyers, and other printable items will be available to download directly from the website, transitioning AI-Mind from online to the real-life space of stakeholders.

"FAQ" section provides clear and easy-to-grasp explanations for common questions, making the project more accessible and tangible. The section is under expansion and will be updated throughout the project with information regarding artificial intelligence, mild cognitive impairment, dementia, AI-Mind solution, and EU funding.

All the website functionality is provided in an intuitive and user-friendly manner. Furthermore, it has a responsive design, i.e., an adapted interface when viewed on mobile devices or tablets, which makes it easy to navigate on a small screen and guarantees convenient access to the website from anywhere.

5 Technical implementation

The AI-Mind website is implemented in a way that allows easy maintenance and provides an appealing experience to its users.

5.1 WordPress

Figure 1: WordPress Logo

The website has been created with the online website creating tool WordPress. The tool offers flexible and professional layouts, various additional plugins to integrate interactive features and adjust the website to the project's needs. By default, it also offers responsive designs, i.e. website layouts that adapt to different screen sizes. The website is based on the scroll-down movement to simplify navigation through the broad content available in the future.

Posts are displayed in reverse chronological order so that the most recent news entry is shown at the top of the page. As the number of posts grows, tags, such as the month of publication or the topic, will be added to each post so that the users can filter them according to their needs and interest.

5.2 Plugins

The website offers various functionalities with the aim of incorporating more upon the project's needs in the future. The most relevant are:

Formidable is used to create tailored questionnaires and contact forms to collect information from interested stakeholders. This can be extended to short surveys, quizzes to increase users' engagement.

Polylang allows switching between languages. This functionality will be implemented mainly in the "Study Participants" and "For Professionals" pages, to address the country-specific sites: Italian, Finnish, Spanish, and Norwegian. English is set up as the default language.

5.3 Theme

The theme has been customised and adjusted by accelCH, following the project's visual identity, and increasing readability. The project's visual identity was defined, including the font Heebo used in different sizes for titles and body text to enhance the lecture flow. Links are displayed in the AI-Mind colours, namely dark green and dark blue, or as engaging buttons with changing colors, redirecting the user to a new website with complementary information. The text colour was set to dark grey to enhance readability.

5.4 Images & graphics

To make the website more appealing to a wide audience, images and graphics are strategically incorporated in the layout to help illustrate the information. This includes using: i) photos that align with the specific content of the page, placed on the header of each page, ii) charts illustrating the concept for the AI-Mind solution, iii) the customized AI-Mind logo and logos of the Beneficiaries and Partner Organisations, and iv) photo of each team member involved from every participating organisation. The logos and profile pictures used on the website were provided by the respective partners, while other illustrations and graphics were created explicitly for use within the AI-Mind project. More visuals will be created and added throughout the project.

6 Structure

The website follows a cohesive layout throughout pages with the background photo on top of the page that sticks to its position when scrolling. Text and visuals are organized with boxes using the clear background as a contrast to navigate the reader's attention seamlessly through the content.

6.1 Home page

The [homepage](https://www.ai-mind.eu/) is the landing page for first-time access to the website through entering the URL (<https://www.ai-mind.eu/>) in an internet browser (e.g. Firefox), a search engine (e.g. Google), or through a link on a different website (e.g. partner websites). When browsing through the AI-Mind website, users can easily return to the homepage by clicking on the AI-Mind logo, as is common practice for many modern websites.

Figure 1. The Homepage opening header with the AI-Mind logo.

The landing page layout consists of three sections with different content:

A. First, the information-oriented section provides visitors with an overview of the AI-Mind project, by presenting the background, news related to the project, and complementary information. Twitter feed is featured on the right sidebar, with links to the full articles and Tweets, so that returning visitors can experience a dynamic, time-evolving homepage and easily access the newest information on the project’s progress.

Figure 2. The Homepage first information-oriented section, with news and Twitter feeder.

B. The next segment provides key information on the project’s goals, consortium, budget granted by EU, and entities involved.

Figure 3. Key information on the Homepage

C. To make it easier for visitors to get in touch with the AI-Mind team, the contact form is embedded in the landing page as the third section. When visiting the website for the first time, visitors are asked to accept or decline the cookies used on the website.

Figure 4. The contact form on the Homepage.

6.2 Project

The [Project](#) page places the AI-Mind project in the wider perspective of social challenges by presenting background information about dementia, mild cognitive impairment (MCI), and current possibilities offered by the health system. A complementary explanation is given by a short video interview with the project coordinator located in the box right to the text. Users can either watch a video on the page or open it on the YouTube AI-Mind channel.

ABOUT AI-MIND RESEARCH

The goal of research is to reduce the disease's burden by developing new interventions and improving health system efficiency.

Besides time-consuming patient investigations with low discriminative power for dementia risk, current treatment options focus on late symptom management. What are now complex, labour-intensive, costly, and poorly predictive screening methods for mild cognitive impairment (MCI) shall be replaced by automated diagnostic screening tools. These are driven by artificial intelligence to address the urgent need for early accurate diagnosis and risk prediction.

Delaying the decline dementia causes will significantly reduce the overall medical and social costs for patients and lessen the pressure on insurance companies and healthcare systems. Studies have consistently shown that the average medical, non-medical, and indirect costs for individuals with dementia are higher compared to those without dementia.

AI-MIND ENABLES EARLIER PREVENTATIVE THERAPIES

With the currently available technology, many patients receive their diagnosis only after the onset of dementia. As a consequence, there might not be the opportunity to start preventative therapies. For people with mild cognitive impairment (MCI), the dementia risk is almost 30% higher than unaffected individuals. Therefore, we need effective diagnostic tools for early dementia risk assessment and intervention for people with MCI.

AI-Mind will disrupt the clinical setting and significantly impact patients' and doctors' diagnostic journeys. Physicians will have a supportive decision-making tool that is able to identify patients at risk of developing dementia with high probability.

FRAMEWORK

Activities in the AI-Mind are organised in eight integrated work packages (WP) cumulating in the delivery of a cloud-based platform containing AI tools that can quickly analyse data inputs. These work packages will, often in parallel, complete tasks regarding research, governance and scoping (WP1); implementation of results (WP2); innovation and creation of tools (WP3); delivery of prototypes (WP4); piloting (WP5); and market outreach (WP6 & WP7). The innovation management (WP8) will ensure effective governance for the project.

Figure 5. The Project page with a video with the coordinator presenting the project.

Organized in a clear way, a short text describes the concept that lies in the heart of the AI-Mind project as well as the project's ambitions. Tailor-made visuals help visitors to better understand not only the solution that will be developed but also how impactful it will be on patients' journey.

Figure 6. Illustration of AI-Mind concept on the Project page.

Considering that elderly people might have difficulties when reading on screens, clickable graphics expand to their full size in a separate window. With the “zoom” button people can enlarge them upon wish and make information even more readable.

Figure 7. Illustration of patient’s journey in zoomed mode.

The “FAQ” section gives a list of frequently asked questions. This part provides a go-to point for non-technical stakeholders, with simplified and clear explanations to reach a wide audience. This maximizes the interest and involvement of the website viewers by improving their understanding of the AI-Mind project. It will be expanded throughout the project.

Figure 8. Frequently asked questions (FAQ) section on the Project page.

6.3 Study participants

The “Study participants” page is under development. A “Study participants” button in the main navigation bar will redirect visitors to the dedicated page.

To support recruitment strategies of AI-Mind partners, accelCH has established structure, functionalities, and content for “Study Participants”. The main target group of this page is potential participants, identified as people with MCI of age between 60-75 years, who may not be familiar with the study. To inform potential participants in an easily understandable way about the AI-Mind study, an explanatory video will be embedded on the page. More information in a form of the text will follow in the next section.

WHAT IS MCI?

Mild cognitive impairment (MCI), an intermediate condition between normal brain ageing and dementia.

It's characterized by problems with memory, language, thinking or judgment increasing over time.

WANT TO KNOW MORE?

See our FAQ section below.

Figure 9. The explanatory video.

FAQ

Figure 10. Information about the study.

Next to that, a “FAQ” section will provide further answers regarding mild cognitive impairment, dementia, or artificial intelligence.

Figure 11. FAQ section with questions regarding the study.

People interested in participation can check directly on the page if they are eligible by answering anonymously few questions in an online questionnaire based on the study inclusion criteria.

CAN YOU PARTICIPATE IN THE STUDY?

Are you between 60 and 75 years?

Yes
 No

Do you experience mild difficulties in everyday routine?

Yes, I find it sometimes difficult to follow all daily tasks
 No, I mark no problems in a daily life

Have you noticed cognitive problems increasing over time?

Yes, I noticed memory and concentration decrease over time
 No, I have not noticed increasing problems

Have you had a cognitive test performed by your doctor?

Yes, my doctor run cognitive tests
 No, my doctor never proposed cognitive tests

Do you often lose your train of thought or the thread of conversations, books or movies?

Yes, I often lose the track
 No, I follow the thread

SUBMIT

Figure 12. A short questionnaire for potential study participants.

A poly-language function has been set for the page. By changing a flag icon in the navigation bar, visitors can switch between English, Norwegian, Italian, Finnish, and Spanish. The “Study participants” page will not only provide information in the local language about the study enrolment, study aims, and inclusion criteria but will give an easy way to contact the respective study location. Furthermore, team members from each study location will be listed in a photo gallery with a direct email address and specific location for contact purposes.

CONTACT OUR TEAM

 E#AIL@ADDRESS.COM

 054 345 44 56

DR. IRA HARALDSEN

Figure 13. Contact information of study team.

6.4 For professionals

The “For professionals” page is under development. This page is tailored to healthcare professionals and will provide relevant information, notably on the study protocol, data protection, and benefits from collaboration with the AI-Mind. Professionals can contact the study team via a clickable button. This page will include a poly-language option as well. By changing a flag icon in the navigation bar, visitors can switch between English, Norwegian, Italian, Finnish, and Spanish.

6.5 Partners

The [Partners](#) page provides details of the AI-Mind consortium with links to their respective websites, brief descriptions of each partner highlighting their expertise, as well as profile pictures and names of the team members involved in the project. An interactive map represents the AI-Mind consortium network in an attractive way that allows not only to zoom in and out but also to select individual partners from a list and see their exact locations. Links to the partners’ websites are assigned to the site markers and redirect the user to the desired page in a new window.

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NETWORK

The AI-Mind consortium brings together a multi-disciplinary, multisectorial and multi-national network to facilitate a paradigm shift in clinical practice away from complex and poorly predictive screening methods and toward automated diagnostic screening tools driven by artificial intelligence. Our network comprises medical experts and opinion leaders on dementia from five hospitals, international experts in brain signal analysis and computer science embedded in **NORA** and **CLAIRE**, four SMEs and academic spin-off companies, patient and professional stakeholders and health technology assessment experts.

Figure 14. General information about consortium with an interactive map on the Partners page.

ACCELOPMENT Schweiz AG is a Swiss SME that assists research institutions and companies in EU project management and the dissemination and exploitation of project results. We are specialised in European research, development and innovation support initiatives, such as Horizon 2020 and the SME focused Eurostars programme. accelCH's multi-disciplinary and highly qualified staff (currently 18) has more than 25 years of experience individually in EU and national funded projects in Health, Biochemistry, eHealth, Materials and other areas. accelCH is currently involved as in **MORE THAN 25 EU FUNDED PROJECTS** (mostly Horizon 2020) and partner organisation in 22 MSCA training networks. ACCEL is ISO 9001 certified and internationally accredited by **IQNET**.

Dr. Jeanette
Müller

Andreia Cruz

Figure 15. Partner description with profile pictures.

6.6 Research & innovation

The [Research & Innovation](#) page includes details on technological, innovative, and application aspects of the AI-Mind project. This page is mainly addressed to the scientific community (researchers in neuroscience, computer science, the scientific community in general), healthcare providers, clinicians, and policymakers. The page will be enriched with visuals and updated with project outcomes, such as data processing, AI models, digital platforms, or implementation into the health system, throughout the project duration.

6.7 News & events

The [News & Events](#) page features short blog posts published whenever there is a worthy update regarding the AI-Mind project, or when news articles and any other related communication item of interest is released. A right sidebar currently shows the Archive by month of publication. Once the number of news items will start to grow, these will also be tagged, based on their topic so the viewers can easily sort through them based on their specific interests. A left sidebar gives a quick overview of the events relevant to the AI-Mind project. This consists of conferences, workshops, or webinars organized by AI-Mind or in which AI-Mind partners participate.

The page can be reached via the corresponding item in the main navigation menu or through the latest news items hyperlinked on the AI-Mind homepage. Each news and event post is linked to its separate page, meaning that each post has an individual URL that can be shared.

Figure 16. Calendar with events on the left, news in the centre, and archive with old posts on the right bar.

Publications on [ScienceX](#), [Alzheimer Europe](#), and [CORDIS](#) can be accessed via 3 dedicated boxes, respectively.

Figure 17. Press releases available via clickable boxes.

6.8 Header & footer

The AI-Mind project increases its impact by being present on social media, namely Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Instagram. Moreover, the AI-Mind has its YouTube channel with the first video already published. Respective icons in both header & footer of every page, give easy access to these digital platforms to all stakeholders. To boost the outreach, information published on these channels is tailored not only to target audiences but is given in a way that aligns with the platform-specific requirements.

Figure 18. Website Header.

GDPR: To comply with the new General Data Protection Regulation, the website includes a cookie banner with an opt-in option for the usage of cookies. Additionally, the [Privacy Policy](#) and [Cookie Policy](#) pages have been updated and complemented with GDPR specific information.

Figure 19. Website Footer.

7 Development & maintenance

accelCH regularly updates the website and collects ideas and inputs from all AI-Mind partners. The project coordinator and accelCH decide on the publication of new inputs for the website (IP issues might arise).

accelCH updates the news & events section on a regular basis with upcoming events or news articles related to or of interest to the AI-Mind project and its stakeholders.

accelCH updates pages dedicated to the AI-Mind study with relevant documents available to download (print materials for communication purposes).

8 Outreach & evaluation

accelCH will measure the website's outreach with Google Analytics, which offers not only the possibility to track website traffic (e.g. page views, unique visitors), but can also detect the immediate impact of dissemination activities that lead to more page views. The outreach will then be evaluated to see if targets have been reached and to identify new outreach measures if necessary.

9 Outlook

As the project progresses, the structure of the AI-Mind website will be adapted by accelCH to include relevant information and new pages when needed. More specifically, next to the above-mentioned "Study Participants" and "For professionals" pages, another page will be added to the main navigation bar at a later stage in the project, namely "Results".

Implementation of the "Results" page is planned when project results will start to be documented in the form of journal articles, posters, conference presentations, infographics, and similar material. These will all be linked to their respective source websites and a search function will be included within the "Results" page, so that the viewer can easily find the documents of interest-based on author names, topic, or date of publication.

"Brain collection" will be a dedicated area on the website to introduce and share existing schemes for dementia prevention and intervention; for example, via online courses offered by OUS and Alzheimer

Europe. Space will include related news outside the project and will work as a hub for all people interested in dementia prevention and intervention.

Overall, all pages will be updated with additional visual material as the project progresses, to ensure a visually pleasing, clear, and engaging experience for the website viewer. This includes embedded videos, an event calendar, photos from conferences, webinars and workshops, illustrations, slideshows, and other multimedia features that align with the AI-Mind visual identity.